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and Supply Chains (IJMVSC)**

**ISSN: 0976 - 979X (Online);
2230 -7966 (print)**

<http://airccse.org/journal/mvsc/ijmvsc.html>

SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT IN INDIAN AUTOMOTIVE INDUSTRY : COMPLEXITIES, CHALLENGES AND WAY AHEAD

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ABSTRACT

The Indian automotive industry, comprising vehicle and component manufacturers, has grown steadily since the economic liberalization of the early 1990's. The arrival of major global auto companies has galvanised the domestic sector into adopting Supply Chain best practices. This has enhanced competitiveness leading to a quantum growth in exports. However, the Indian automotive industry has to operate in a unique environment further posing challenges to the already complex automobile supply chain. Therefore, a need is felt to continually study supply chain practices in this sector from a contemporary, practitioner's viewpoint in order to identify key factors of differentiation which would ultimately provide competitive advantage. This paper seeks to understand the present status, complexities and challenges facing the Indian automobile sector. It examines trends such as visibility and innovation, collaboration and supply networks and evolving leadership roles impacting supply chain effectiveness. Strategies for overcoming challenges are presented as also a framework for further study and analysis.

KEYWORDS

Supply Chain Management, automotive industry, Supply Chain Challenges, Assembler-supplier synergy, India

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Exploring the fourth wave of supermarket evolution: concepts of value and complexity in Africa

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Abstract

The increase in urban development and an increasingly stable and economically empowered middle class in Africa are both driving the expansion of supermarket activity in these new, lucrative, African markets. Much of this activity comes from South Africa and has triggered what can be seen as the "fourth wave" of global supermarket evolution. This paper reviews the background, examines the expansion of three major South African supermarket businesses into the African continent, and assesses the impact on local producers of goods and services. It does so by introducing the concept of value chain to reveal some of the new complexities in this process and to show how some of the issues associated with value must be mitigated so that there can be a successful marriage between the traditional and new business practices in the host country economies. The discussion and analysis is based on a range of interviews with senior management in the three South African retailers.

Keywords

Africa, Retail, Supermarket, Supply chain, Value chain, local suppliers

<http://airccse.org/journal/mvsc/papers/3312ijmvsc03.pdf>

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THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN ORGANIZATIONAL INNOVATIONS, INTERNAL SOURCES OF KNOWLEDGE AND ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

Management research considers knowledge as one of the first sources of competitiveness of the company. This observation is at the origin of development in recent years, the Knowledge-Based View (Grant, 1996), resulting from the resource-based perspective approach. This research examines the importance of internal sources of knowledge and its relationship with organizational innovation and organizational performance. We did this research on a sample of 200 Tunisian companies operating in different sectors. Our study was built mainly on the basis of quantitative method. The data collection method is the questionnaire as part of a hypothetical-deductive approach and the mode of administration is self-administered survey and e-mail survey. The empirical verification of the assumptions of this research has led us to confirm the relationship between internal and external sources of knowledge with organizational innovation and organizational performance and to infirm the relationship between organizational innovation and organizational performance.

KEYWORDS

Organizational innovation, internal sources of knowledge, organizational performance.

<http://airccse.org/journal/mvsc/papers/6115ijmvsc05.pdf>

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VALUE CHAIN MODEL FOR STEEL MANUFACTURING SECTOR: A CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Michael E Porter developed a value chain model for manufacturing sector with five primary activities and four supporting activities. The value chain model developed by Porter is extended to a steel manufacturing sector due to expansions of steel plants has become a continual process for their growth and survival. In this paper a value chain model for steel manufacturing sector is developed considering five primary activities and six support activities.

KEYWORDS

Value chain model, steel manufacturing sector, integrated steel plant, primary activities, supporting activities.

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HIDDEN COSTS OF QUALITY: MEASUREMENT & ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

Quality is the assurance of adherence to the customer specifications and it is a measure of excellence or a state of being free from defects, deficiencies and significant variation from standards. Customer specification of the product can be met by strictly adhering to the quality control measures in the production process and can be ensured in a cost effective manner only if the quality of each and every process in the organization is well defined and ensured without any lapses. Every activity in the supply chain line to be critically verified to identify the quality deviations incurring additional expense or loss to the organization. This is in line with the continual improvement principle of TQM philosophy . The cost of quality management system acts as the most significant tool in measuring, monitoring, controlling and decision making activities in a firm which aims on business excellence.

KEY WORDS

Quality Cost, Hidden costs, Opportunity costs, Pareto Diagram, Quality Management System.

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FAST FASHION IN THE MOROCCAN APPAREL SUPPLY CHAIN: A CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

The apparel supply chain is a dynamic industry made distinctive by demand uncertainty and the handling of very many Stock Keeping Units (SKUs) during one season, which make it impossible to forecast demand accurately. Hence, apparel brands have to continuously maintain reactivity to the changing trends in consumer fashion tastes through quickly creating new designs that are suitable for all customers with affordable prices. In this context, fashion retailers adopting a new approach called fast fashion raised. In this paper, we will examine at first, from a literature review, the emergence of fast fashion model especially the ZARA Case. Then by conducting semi-structured interviews, we will analyze DIAMANTINE (a Moroccan fashion retailer brand) fast fashion model and identify the way of its success from a supply chain management perspective.

KEYWORDS

Fast Fashion; ZARA; DIAMANTINE; Moroccan apparel Supply Chain

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A CASE STUDY ON CONSTRAINTS AFFECTING THE PRODUCTIVITY OF READYMADE GARMENT (RMG) INDUSTRY IN BANGLADESH

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ABSTRACT

The success of Readymade garment (RMG) exports from Bangladesh over the past few decades has reached to an unprecedented height and sometimes it goes beyond optimistic expectations compared to any other sectors in the country. Being one of the lucrative multibillion dollar industries, it has provided more than 4.0 million employment opportunities and ensured women empowerment. It has brought the fortune to rural women communities and they have become independent by themselves. The garment industry in Bangladesh faces a number of challenges including fallacious working condition, dearth of safety, political turbulence and, low remuneration. To sustain in the competitive global market, management has to identify the prime key opportunities and identify any threats. This study was conducted to analyze the prospects and constraints of Bangladesh RMG industry using well known multi-criteria decision making (MCDM) method namely analytic hierarchy process (AHP). To judge the model, data was collected through the focus group discussion and key informant interviews with the managers of three different garment industries situated in Gazipur, Bangladesh. The findings of the study showed that “unsound working condition” among several challenges affects workers working capability and productivity severely. The study recommends that through proper identification and taking corrective measures against the challenges by the management of RMG sector, Bangladesh has the opportunity to be the market leader in this sector.

KEYWORDS

Readymade garment; Productivity; Competitiveness; Constraints; Multi criteria decision making; Analytic hierarchy process.

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TREND ANALYSIS OF CAR RECALLS: EVIDENCE FROM THE US MARKET

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ABSTRACT

Influenced by Toyota's recent automobile recalls 2009-2010, and highlighting the importance of recalls research, this study conducts a car recalls trend analysis for the US market that is a first of its kind. The research uses secondary data from recall websites maintained by public and private organizations. The study shows recalls are a common event with the majority of recalls initiated by only a few carmakers. Though carmakers use many eye catching and popular quality and customer care slogans and programs, many popular car makers still face valid customer complaints and consequently face many unwanted recalls. Results of automobile recall trends analysis will be beneficial for car makers, government authorities who deal with recalls, insurance companies, and researchers.

KEYWORDS

Automotive recalls, product recalls, reverse logistics, closed loop supply chain

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THE INFLUENCE OF INDIVIDUAL FACTORS ON THE ENTREPRENEURIAL INTENTION

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ABSTRACT

Today, no one is safe from forces and pressures, which are exerted on it, because of a significant number of the requirements in particular as regards competitiveness, the need for change, or the crises and the deregulations. In front of the economic and social turbulences which we know, the creation of new company appears as a cause of general interest. This research papers focuses on the problematic of the entrepreneurship, and more particularly on the stake which this domain represents in our society, by treating the determinants of the entrepreneurial intention. To face this news gives, students must reconsider their behaviors and their practices to renew themselves, to open out and reinforce their position in the market. Some of these practices form what one calls the entrepreneurial orientation. For this reason, we will devote this paper for better encircling and apprehending the concept of individual factors, and we tried to know how the individual factors (motivations, need for accomplishment, need for autonomy, passion to develop its own idea, individual characteristics, work experience, teaching) can influence the intention of the entrepreneur to create his own project. We focused on review literature through a survey of a sample of students from the Higher Institute of Business Administration of Sfax (Tunisia).

KEYWORDS

individual factors, motivational, need for achievement, need for autonomy, passion to develop its own idea, individual characteristics, work experience, teaching, intention.

<http://airccse.org/journal/mvsc/papers/5414ijmvsc04.pdf>

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ISSUES AND CHALLENGES IN THE SUPPLY CHAIN OF FRUITS & VEGETABLES SECTOR IN INDIA: A REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Purpose- The entire supply chain of Fruits and Vegetables in India is laden with various issues and challenges. To list the possible challenges and suggest a way forward, there is a need to study the supply chain of Fruits and Vegetables sector in India. So the purpose of this paper is to discuss the supply chain of fruits and vegetables sector in India and explain the issues which are affecting it. Authors also suggested the corresponding mitigation strategies to overcome the identified issues and challenges. Design/methodology/approach-Descriptive research has been used for this study. The supply chain of Fruits and Vegetables sector has been explained and attempt has been made towards identifying the issues affecting the supply chain of the sector. The present study undertakes a thorough review of basic and contemporary literature available and tries to explain the factors affecting the supply chain of Fruits and Vegetables sector in India. The literature has been divided into various themes according to the issues in the supply chain and an investigation has been attempted to identify various factors affecting the supply chain.

KEYWORDS

Fruits & Vegetables, Supply Chain Management, Inefficiency, Infrastructure, Wastage.

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Volume Link : <http://airccse.org/journal/mvsc/vol6.html>

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